

RRP Edge Computing System

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Abstract—Due to the popularity of the Internet of Things, more and more computing resources are needed for smart devices. To relieve the dependency on clouds and to lower the cost of equipment, we propose a Regularity-based Resource Partition Edge Computing System (RRP-ECS). In this system, RRP divides each CPU into 2 partitions, one of which handles the basic control, while the other functions as a core of a virtual machine dealing with intensive tasks. We introduce a centralized structure and discuss the critical task mapping problem in RRP-ECS in detail.

I. INTRODUCTION

As a part of the Internet of Things (IoT), more and more smart devices are deployed in homes and cities these days. However, smart devices require a large amount of computing resources. Dedicated localized computing resources are expensive while dependency on cloud computing leads to inevitable latency. This paper proposes an edge computing system based on the Regularity-based Resource Partition (RRP) model [1].

Considering that smart devices do not have heavy-loaded tasks at all times, equipping a high performance CPU for each smart device would be expensive and wasteful. Therefore, equipping a relatively low-configuration CPU for each smart device and sharing computing resources with each other would be less expensive and more efficient. RRP Edge Computing System (RRP-ECS) is a virtual machine built on multiple smart devices as shown in Fig. 1.

For smart devices, tasks can be divided into two classes: 1) *basic control tasks*, which are fundamental and low-cost, and 2) *high-level intensive tasks*, e.g., analyzing the data collected from sensors. Similarly, in RRP-ECS, each computing resource, i.e., CPU, is divided into two partitions by the RRP model as shown in the dotted squares in Fig. 1. Then, we can assign the basic control tasks of the device, e.g., monitoring temperatures, to the **reserved** partition. For instance, in Fig. 1, Partitions 1, 3 up to $n - 1$ are reserved partitions that work on basic control tasks independently. We refer to other partitions as **redundant** partitions as they are not necessary for basic controls. Hence, we can utilize the redundant partitions across different devices, just like Partitions 2, 4 up to n in Fig. 1, to build a virtual machine (VM). Each partition has a VCPU pinned on it while Host OS runs the Application Level on these VCPUs. High-level tasks of smart devices are uploaded to VM where they are accordingly allocated to partitions. Besides, with a host OS installed in VM, the VM can also be connected

through a personal computer and handle the tasks uploaded by users.

There are several advantages of adopting RRP-ECS.

- 1) **Efficiency**: With an efficient algorithm dividing resources into partitions [1] at the resource level, redundant computing resources in smart devices can be utilized efficiently to assist other smart devices instead of being idle.
- 2) **Security**: RRP guarantees that reserved partitions can work independently without interrupts from other partitions albeit they are located on the same physical core and thus the security of basic control tasks is guaranteed.
- 3) **Portability**: Different smart objects always have heterogeneity in either hardware or software. With the centralized structure introduced later, the addition and removal of CPUs in RRP-ECS are less costly. Similarly, other resources, e.g., hard disk, can easily be included or removed with a centralized manager.
- 4) **Transparency**: With all tasks managed by the VM, if the local computing resource is not enough, VM can directly get connected to the cloud. Thus the cloud connection and resource usage are transparent to Applications.

The remainder of this paper discusses: 1) The structure of RRP-ECS. 2) The resource interface provided by the RRP model. 3) Potential strategies that map tasks to partitions and their performances.

II. THE STRUCTURE OF RRP-ECS

As shown in Fig. 1, Virtual machine consists of different partitions in the resource level. Then a host OS is run on the resource level where applications are deployed. In this section, we show how these are done based on the centralized structure of RRP-ECS. It is worth mentioning that reserved partitions work independently and are not included in the VM and there is **only one VM** which employs the centralized structure as shown in Fig. 2.

In the centralized structure, the Task Manager (TM) is responsible for allocating tasks to partitions and is similar in functionalities to the Domain 0 of Xen [2], that has access to the hardware. The function of TM includes: managing the tasks coming from other partitions, maintaining device drivers and communicating hardware information to partitions. TM starts first during the booting of the system and then starts managing redundant partitions. In a nutshell, TM acts as a nerve center for the VM. Due to limitations of space, we mainly focus on the task processing, which is the main function of TM.

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Fig. 1: A two-level resource partitioning framework.

Tasks from different Applications are all managed by TM. To be specific, there are two sources of tasks. 1) Smart devices: High-level intensive tasks from smart devices are uploaded to TM. 2) Host OS: The host OS installed in the VM can be reached through Secure Shell (SSH) like cloud. Tasks uploaded through the connection are also uploaded to TM.

TM processes the tasks with the following operations, which is also shown in Fig. 2.

- 1) **upload()**: Tasks from different sources are uploaded to TM through upload().
- 2) **map()**: After being uploaded, tasks are put into a global queue, where the LLF (least laxity first) policy [3] is adopted. Tasks popped out from the queue will be mapped to a suitable partition for execution if there exists one.
- 3) **dispatch()**: If a task is successfully mapped to a partition, it will be transmitted to the partition through event channels and executed there. Event channels are built based on TCP/IP [2].
- 4) **upload_cloud()**: If no partitions can finish the task on time, it will be uploaded to the cloud and taken good care of there [4].

The advantages of adopting a centralized structure in RRP-ECS are as follows. 1) With a centralized TM, which acts like Domain 0 in Xen, merely installing a drive on CPUs in smart devices can include them in RRP-ECS. This makes the removal and addition of devices easier. 2) A centralized structure makes the connection to the resource level, i.e., clouds and partitions, transparent to Applications. 3) A centralized structure reduces the communications between partitions, which may lead the system to potential intrusions or vulnerability.

With a centralized TM, the biggest challenge for RRP-ECS is developing policy mapping tasks to partitions. Without a proper policy, tasks may be assigned to a partition where it cannot be completed on time. Therefore, a schedulability test on each partition and a proper mapping policy are much required. To better understand this, we introduce the resource interface provided by RRP.

III. RESOURCE INTERFACE PROVIDED BY THE RRP MODEL

We first formally define a **time slice**.

Fig. 2: Centralized Task-Partition Architecture.

Definition 1: Time slice is the basic unit of time containing fixed number of cycles that cannot be further partitioned in any given resource partition.

Based on time slices, RRP divides computing resources into partitions efficiently based on **availability factors** and **supply regularities**. Availability factor $\alpha(A)$ shows how many time slices a certain partition A takes from the CPU during the hyper-period. Supply regularity $k(A)$ shows how close A is to an average distribution [1]. In this paper, we are only going to discuss regular partition whose supply regularity is 1.

Regular partitions are punctual as shown in Theorem 1.

Theorem 1: A regular partition A will have exactly one time slice every $\frac{1}{\alpha(A)}$ time slices.

The proof of Theorem 1 is given in the technical report [5].

The resource interface of a regular partition is simply the **availability factor** α . Thanks to the definition of time slice, the availability factor can be applied to evaluate the computing ability of partitions located on uniform processors.

IV. TASK MAPPING PROBLEM

Since [6] already proves that scheduling a task set on a partition is the same as scheduling a task set on a CPU, we will not discuss the scheduling of tasks on a single partition here. With the structure in Section II and the resource interface provided by the RRP illustrated in Section III, the main challenge of RRP-ECS is to make sure the mapping policy in map() neither makes partitions overloaded nor waste enormous resources. For that, we first introduce a schedulability test to judge whether a task is schedulable on a partition.

A. Schedulability test for task mapping problem in RRP-ECS

We first define the task set: $T = \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n\}$. Each task T_i is defined by $T_i = (c_i, d_i, p_i, R_i, D_i, V_i)$. c_i , d_i and p_i respectively refer to the Worst Case Execution Time (WCET), the relative deadline, and the period of the task. V_i is the value of T_i , which is the reward for accomplishing T_i on time. R_i is the arrival time of the task. No information of T_i can be accessed before R_i .

Similarly, D_i is the departure time of task T_i . A periodic task T_i does not leave the system, i.e., $D_i = +\infty$. Sporadic tasks, on the other hand, are split by TM into multiple single-instance sporadic tasks. Hence, a single-instance sporadic task

T_k has a departure time $D_k = R_k + \min(d_k, p_k)$ since it is supposed to leave once its execution is done.

The regular partition set is $\mathbb{P} = \{\mathbb{P}_1, \mathbb{P}_2, \dots, \mathbb{P}_m\}$. Each partition \mathbb{P}_j is defined by the resource interface $\mathbb{P}_j = (\alpha_j)$ where α_j is the availability factor of \mathbb{P}_j .

We give the schedulability test for tasks on a regular partition.

Theorem 2: A task set T is schedulable on a regular partition \mathbb{P}_j if

$$\sum_{i=1}^{|T|} \frac{c_i}{\min\{d_i, p_i\}} \leq \alpha_j \quad (1)$$

The proof of Theorem 2 is included in the technical report [5]. It is worth mentioning that, for implicit task sets, Equation 1 is the necessary and sufficient condition.

With Theorem 2, we can further define the notation of density.

Definition 2: The density of a task T_i is

$$DEN_i = \frac{c_i}{\min\{d_i, p_i\}} \quad (2)$$

B. Model Formulation

Now we formulate the mapping problem. We first consider the model consists of only periodic tasks involved. The constraints are as discussed below.

- **Schedulability constraint:** The sum of the densities of tasks allocated to a certain partition P_i should not exceed α_i to keep tasks real-time according to Theorem 2.
- **Fair constraint:** A task will be abandoned only when no partition can accommodate it because RRP-ECS is not allowed to abandon tasks freely.
- **Online constraint:** No information regarding task T_i can be known before its arrival time R_i .
- **Non-migration constraint:** Once a task is assigned to a partition, it cannot be migrated to another partition or removed from the system until its departure time.

With the above constraints, the ultimate goal is to maximize the expression:

$$\max \sum_{i=1}^n x_i V_i \quad (3)$$

In equation 3, x_i is a binary variable showing whether T_i is accomplished on time. If T_i is accomplished on time, $x_i = 1$, else $x_i = 0$. When $x_i = 0$, T_i will be uploaded to the cloud

and executed there because the resource in RRP-ECS cannot fulfill its request on time.

We name this model Regular-partitions Periodic tasks Mapping (RPM). Similarly, we can formulate Regular-partitions Composite tasks Mapping (RCM) consists of both periodic and sporadic tasks.

For RCM, all constraints and the goal above remain the same while a new constraint is added.

- **Leaving constraint:** No resources will be reserved for task T_i after D_i .

The goal of RCM is also to maximize the values gained as shown in Equation 3.

For both RPM and RCM, we mainly consider two sorts of value of tasks. 1) Unit case: All tasks are equally important, i.e., $V_i = 1, \forall i \in [1, n]$. 2) General case: The value of each task is decided by the user arbitrarily. Here we do not discuss the proportional case where $V_i = DEN_i$ due to space limitations, but it is discussed in the technical report [5].

C. Compare and contrast

Though RRP has been extensively studied since its proposal[1, 6], mapping tasks to partitions has never been discussed because this is the first time RRP is used to integrate distributed resources into one VM.

Despite that RPM and RCM resemble task mapping on uniform processors and Multiple Knapsack Problem (MKP), some characteristics distinguish RPM and RCM from models in former works. 1) Both RPM and RCM are online models, while many decent works are done in offline scenarios [7, 8]. The lack of preliminary information and long response time requirements prevent offline algorithms from solving the online version. 2) Both densities of tasks and the availability factors of partitions do not have basic unit size, thus breaking the assumption that the capacity of bins and size of items are integers [9]. 3) The fair constraint does not allow the system to abandon tasks freely unlike the removable cases of online MKP [10].

Therefore, RPM and RCM are different from former models. The solutions applied to solve them, however, decides the efficiency of RRP-ECS. Next, we give our observations.

D. Algorithm Best-Fit

Our answer towards RPM and RCM is quite simple: Best Fit (BF). In BF, we use a set of parameter $\{\beta_j\}$ to record

Fig. 3: Performance of various algorithms with variable ratios (λ) between total utilization of tasks and total availability factors of partitions in RPM.

Fig. 4: Performance of various algorithms with variable ratios (λ) between total utilization of tasks and total availability factors of partitions in RCM and the influence of Periodic Ratio in RCM.

the capacity of corresponding partitions $\{\mathbb{P}_j\}$. Initially, we set $\beta_j = \alpha_j$. For task T_i , BF chooses partition P_k satisfying Equation 4. The key idea of BF is to reserve partitions with large capacities for the future.

$$k = \min_{j: \beta_j \geq DEN_i} \beta_j \quad (4)$$

Though maximization problem in RPM and RCM are both NP-hard problem in strong sense [8] because they are variants of MKP, we prove a constant competitive ratio for BF on accommodating inputs [11].

Theorem 3: Let ω be an accommodating sequence [11], $BF(\omega)$, the result of BF on ω and $OPT(\omega)$, the result of the offline optimal algorithm on ω satisfies: $\frac{BF(\omega)}{OPT(\omega)} \geq \frac{1}{2}$. The proof of Theorem 3 is illustrated in the technical report [5].

Intuitively speaking, BF performs well because it always reserves the resource for the unknown future. It may not be a good strategy in offline scenarios [8], but BF performs really well by being prudent in online scenarios. Next we validate the performance of BF through simulations¹.

To make the simulation more realistic, we only pass in the sum of the availability factors of partitions and the sum of densities of tasks. The number of partitions and tasks as well as the specific parameters of each partition and task are all randomly generated. Each simulation is repeated 1,000,000 times and the results shown are the average value of results. Best Fit is compared with Worst Fit (WF) and First Fit (FF), which are prominent online algorithms discussed before [12].

We measure the result by **Schedulability**, which reveals the percentage of the task sets that are schedulable and **Values Gained Ratio**, which is the ratio between values gained by the system and the total values of all tasks.

According to Fig. 3 and 4, the performance of BF always overwhelms FF and WF with obvious gaps in all measurements and few tasks fail when BF is applied even for heavily-loaded task sets. Under different Periodic Ratio, which is the ratio between the number of periodic tasks and that of all tasks, BF still performs better throughout as shown in Fig. 4d. The gap between BF and other algorithms increase as the Periodic Ratio increases since a higher periodic ratio implies a heavier load. This heavy load can be attributed to the fact that periodic

tasks never leave the system. More simulations are presented in the technical report [5]. In short, all simulations indicate that BF performs well even when the resource is limited and it can guarantee the efficiency of RRP-ECS in most cases.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes an edge computing system RRP-ECS and discusses the centralized structure. Based on the resource interface provided by RRP, we further discuss the task mapping problem and provide a brief and an efficient response with Best Fit which is further validated by simulations.

However, we still have several potential to-do tasks which can be pursued in the future regarding RRP-ECS.

- With no theoretical obstacles, the next step is to implement RRP-ECS on Xen.
- The feasibility of using caches (levels L1, 2 & 3) to accelerate the scheduling and provide real-time guarantee in TM needs to be investigated.
- The simulation codes used in this paper provide an environment for the development of Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithms in RPM and RCM based on Keras [13].

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¹Simulation codes: <https://github.com/DDeChoU/TaskMappingSimulation>